

EDUCATIONAL GAMES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ESP CLASSES

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Abstract

Teaching ESP occupies an important role in a modern university and is an important component in the professional training of specialists for many sectors of activity. The use of game-based methods of teaching English is becoming increasingly relevant and practical. The smart mix of conventional teaching methods with new gaming technology helps to create a creative atmosphere in the classroom and boosts student motivation in teaching ESP.

Key words.

English for Special Purposes (ESP), game technologies, higher professional education, effectiveness, teaching.

INTRODUCTION

English for Special Purposes (ESP) is currently taught in a variety of settings worldwide. Since the 1960s, when ESP was first discussed as a separate area of teaching English as a foreign language, this aspect of teaching English has grown significantly and has taken a leading role in teaching English for professional purposes. [S. M. Davronov, 1019] Specialists in any industry require, in addition to traditional training, a tool that allows for the efficient and effective transmission of professional information in the context of the dynamic evolution of the process of international integration and information exchange.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this regard, it should be noted that when beginning a career as an ESP teacher, most teaching practitioners struggle to analyse students' needs. They are unable to resolve situations and problems due to a lack of knowledge. In higher education, a significant arsenal of various game methods for teaching ESP has been accumulated. I'd like to focus on a few of them that have seen the most widespread application in pedagogical practise. Games as a technique of teaching ESP are distinguished not only by the great activity of the participants, but also by the

heightened intellectual and mental stress of pupils in compared to traditional approaches. Teachers must clearly understand and consider the didactic features of game classes when developing, planning, and teaching them.

A business game is one of the most complex types of gaming activities because it simulates collective professional activity. There are numerous classifications for business games. As a result, the degree of formalisation of games is significant, particularly the relationship between the degree of formalisation of the control object and the freedom to pick control actions, which is particularly important for future ESP teachers. [Dudley-Evans T., St. John M. J., 2018] Meanwhile, too much formalization rigidifies the training game and makes control amorphous. This type of game is better suited for mastering instructions and other professional activity norms, but it does not contribute much to the development of creative skills. The participants' freedom of action makes the game a game, encouraging them to actively express their position.

Business games have typical game characteristics such as dynamism, repetitiveness of steps, a complex combination of possible action alternatives, and time compression when making decisions. Business games differ from other forms of game classes in the following most important features that characterize their didactic properties in teaching ESP: [Hutchinson T., Waters A., 2019]

1. The presence of a significant socioeconomic, socio-psychological, or technical issue that necessitates modeling the professional activities of a large team of specialists in order to be resolved.

2. The presence of a common goal for the entire gaming team, as well as the ability for each player in the game to influence the achievement of the result through his or her actions while working in a specific position.

3. The presence, as in real life, of information uncertainty, various types of failures, deviations, complications, and so on. Decisions are frequently made with incomplete information, posing a risk.

This means that the incompleteness of information should also take place when making decisions in the process of an educational game.

4. The adoption and implementation of a specific sequence of decisions during the game, each of which is dependent on the previous stage's (step's) decision and the actions of other participants.

5. The presence and necessity of a developed incentive system that implements the main functions, such as encouraging each game participant to act as in life, at the limit of their intellectual capabilities; if necessary, subordinating the interests of one or another game participant to the common goal of the team and

ensuring an objective assessment of each student's personal contribution to achieving the common goal, the overall result of the game team.

CONCLUSION

If the teacher wants to be successful in his work with the group, he must search for and adapt game technologies, new and innovative technologies, and multimedia learning tools and digital technologies, online resources, and mobile applications in the learning process.

Game-based ESP learning mechanisms are rapidly evolving, and it is impossible to cover all current trends in this brief article. Thus, despite the fact that the teaching of ESP is focused on practical professionally oriented application, it is based on knowledge of the nature of the language, knowledge of the basic methods and forms of teaching and learning based on games, just like any other aspect of teaching English.

REFERENCES:

1. Davronov S. M. Pedagogical challenges of ESP teachers// Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies. 2019. Vol. 1. P. 489-493.
3. Dudley-Evans T., St. John M. J. Developments in English for Specific Purposes. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018.
4. Hutchinson T., Waters A. English for Specific Purposes: A Learning Centered Approach. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2019.